

Automated End-to-End AI/ML Lifecycles for Radio Management in 6G Networks

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Abstract—Intelligent radio resource management is expected to play a vital role in addressing the strict user demands, possessing new challenges in the era of 6G services. In this paper, we provide an extensive study of artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) lifecycles, within the open radio access network (O-RAN) framework with particular emphasis on radio resource management advancement. More specifically, considering a multi-layered 6G network system, the AI/ML Cross-Layer Platform (AI-CLatform) is introduced to leverage AI/ML lifecycles devoted for O-RAN operation. With the near real-time RAN intelligent controller (Near-RT RIC) devoted for radio intelligence, special emphasis is given on the development, deployment, optimization, and continuous monitoring of ML models within O-RAN, whereas the interactions between O-RAN and AI-CLatform are justified. To concretely illustrate the proposed end-to-end AI/ML sequential process, we present a proof-of-concept (PoC) practical scenario focusing on intelligent beamforming optimization for proactively managing the interference using recurrent neural networks (RNNs). The quantitative simulation findings prove the potential of the proposed AI/ML framework in enhancing critical 6G network functions within the O-RAN paradigm.

Index Terms—AI/ML lifecycle, O-RAN, AI-CLatform, Near-RT RIC, Beamforming, RNN, and 6G Networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Technological progress today has not been granted without cost. Significant obstacles have emerged, along with critical requirements that impose urgent actions. 5G networks have provided notable advantages, specifically improved speed and capacity, that allowed the development of new applications ranging from the Internet of Things (IoT) to autonomous vehicles. However, several challenges have limited the potential of 5G networks to fully satisfy all the needs, as exten-

sively explored in various research studies [1]. 5G networks in high-frequency bands, necessitate small-cell deployment, potentially increasing infrastructure costs and cybersecurity vulnerabilities. Furthermore, the relative latency limitations for certain applications are currently of crucial significance [2].

The requirements of end-users and operators primarily drive 6G network development, where users anticipate a wide range of applications of high performance, synchronization of latency, and robust security. On the other hand, network operators anticipate efficient resource utilization, energy-efficient operations, and wide network coverage. Generally, 6G networks are expected to reduce energy consumption and support a large number of devices with wide coverage, while enabling a new range of applications, such as holographic communication, high-precision sensing, and extended reality and virtual reality (XR/VR). Furthermore, 6G networks support trust and security mechanisms, mitigating security concerns [3], [4].

With the advent of new 6G technologies, the management of the radio environment has become more challenging, necessitating the utilization of advanced tools. These tools include the utilization of cloud-native infrastructures, and the incorporation of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) capabilities [5]. In addition to the emergence of open radio access networks (O-RAN) which is one of the architectural frameworks, that support interoperability and virtualization in RAN. It is worth noting that when O-RAN combines with service-oriented architectures (SOA), the integration flexibility and efficiency of radio and core network functions increase, facilitating the emergence of more adaptive 6G systems [6]. The primary element in O-RAN is the RAN intelligent controller (RIC), which oversees

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network control functions and can be divided into two categories: Non-real-time RIC (Non-RT-RIC) and Near-RT-RIC. Non-RT-RIC hosts remote applications (rApps) that handle tasks that are not time-sensitive, while Near-RT-RIC time-sensitive tasks that must be completed within a time frame of 10 ms to 1 second. These tasks can be executed by the hosted extended applications (xApps) [7]. Generally, the radio unit (RU), distributed unit (DU), and centralized unit (CU), along with the RIC components and a standardized set of interfaces (E2, A1, O1, O2, and E3), constitute the fundamental structure of open RAN architecture [8]. Furthermore, the concept of AI native in 6G networks, where AI is directly integrated into the network functions [9] is highly promising with O-RAN. It allows for the seamless integration of AI with network slicing, enabling real-time data processing and adaptive network management [10].

Despite all the promising developments, fully exploiting the advantages of AI/ML within the O-RAN remains a challenging area of research. Recent approaches lack thorough, end-to-end solutions for managing the AI/ML lifecycle in O-RAN environments, presenting an essential topic for development to discover the full capabilities of AI-driven network optimization in 6G systems. In this paper, we propose an AI/ML Cross-Layer Platform (AI-CLatform) specifically designed for this purpose. More specifically, a unified framework for the AI/ML lifecycle is presented along with multi-phase sequence diagrams illustrating the interactions between AI-CLatform and O-RAN framework within a general 6G Service-Based Architecture (SBA). The following subsection I-A provides an overview of recent AI/ML research in the 6G system, including a summary of our work contribution.

A. AI/ML in 6G Radio Management

The integration of AI/ML algorithms into the 6G radio systems signifies a crucial transformation [11], as they can extract knowledge from network behaviors to detect failures, optimize network performance, and make proactive decisions [12]. Additionally, ML-driven approaches optimize network management through mechanisms for requesting, receiving, and verifying AI-driven insights [13] and enhance resource allocation by analyzing data generated by numerous devices [14]. Extensive research exhibits that AI/ML platforms improve 6G technologies [15], by enhancing resource allocation, enabling flexible orchestration, and dynamically managing network slices. These platforms also improve integrated sensing and communication systems by enhancing beamforming and reducing self-interference. Moreover, multiple ML algorithms have been utilized in various network technologies, addressing traffic predictions and security concerns challenges.

It is worth noting that many valuable research projects have considered the recent challenges within 6G architecture frameworks, such as the Hexa-X [16], and HexaX-II, to create a more efficient, connected, and resilient digital future, focusing on AI-driven communication. On the other hand, the 6G BRAINS project [17] also explores AI/ML frameworks to enhance industry automation, while the RISE-6G project [18]

Fig. 1. The general 6G architecture

employs AI to improve reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RISs), optimizing network and energy efficiency. As well as, ASSIST-IoT Project [19], utilizes AI/ML frameworks to transform IoT systems, enabling smart decision-making within IoT ecosystems.

However, the increasing complexity of 6G networks and demands for low latency and high security drive the research for further resilient and reliable AI/ML frameworks. This paper presents an O-RAN-compliant AI/ML platform that is operable in multi-layered 6G systems, that can be utilized for supporting cross-layer intelligent functionalities, activating and managing end-to-end AI/ML lifecycles. Also, we outline a multi-phase sequence diagram to illustrate the proposed functionality, call flows of each intelligence phase, and interactions between the AI/ML platform and 6G frameworks within a service-oriented architecture. The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- A general-purpose AI/ML Cross-Layer Platform (AI-CLatform) for end-to-end development, deployment, optimization, and continuous monitoring of AI/ML functionalities for 6G radio management is presented.
- A comprehensive presentation of the complete AI/ML lifecycles and their interactions with the O-RAN framework is outlined. This is demonstrated by a general-purpose, multi-phase and detailed sequence diagram, which visualizes the entire processes involved in the AI/ML model lifespan within the O-RAN context.
- A practical application of this framework is illustrated through a use-case scenario that focuses on a practical AI function (AIF), implemented for intelligent beamforming, supported by promising simulation results.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II presents an overview of 6G architecture. Section III provides a detailed description of AI-CLatform modules supported by sequence diagrams to visualize a comprehensive AI/ML lifecycle. Section IV, demonstrates a simulation scenario for intelligent beamforming, whereas section V concludes the work.

II. GENERAL 6G ARCHITECTURE

The considered 6G architecture, depicted in Fig. 1, consists of three main frameworks as follows:

- 1) Cloud Continuum Framework (CCF): Optimizes resource management across multiple cloud providers, including data centers (DC) and aggregated data centers (ADC), according to the specific needs of applications. It considers key factors such as resource availability, cost, and energy efficiency. This framework relies on AI technologies to continuously monitor and optimize resource usage in real-time.
- 2) Management and Orchestration Framework (MOF): Coordinates the management and orchestration across multiple heterogeneous network domains and cloud environments by relying on master orchestrators (MOs) that coordinate multiple service orchestrators (SOs) simultaneously. MOF enables seamless integration and operation through secure interfaces, while also leveraging AI/ML techniques for advanced optimization and anomaly detection.
- 3) AI/ML Cross-Layer Platform (AI-CLatform): Enables AI-native design by separating AI/ML tasks from control applications on a unified platform. It improves the performance and adaptability of network functions (NFs) by integrating AI/ML for enhanced resource management, and service orchestration. Section III will provide additional information about this framework and its main modules.

In the present architecture, O-RAN functions are integrated into network services (NS), allowing for dynamic allocation and management within specific resource partitions. This allocation is adapted to specific NS requirements, resulting in efficient resource utilization. Within the O-RAN framework, the Near-RT RIC employs xApps for real-time control and optimization, whereas rApps in the Non-RT RIC handle more complex optimization and configuration tasks. These tasks rely on AI-driven insights from the AI-CLatform to improve network performance and efficiency. The core network manages essential NFs using an SBA, which fully collaborates with the NS layer.

The components within the 6G architecture mainly interact with each other through multiple buses, including the M&O bus which connects MOF with other components within the architecture, such as NS, application services (AS), and AI-CLatform functionalities. Additionally, the AI/ML bus connects the AI-CLatform to various NFs throughout the O-RAN and Core, while also supporting AI-as-a-Service (AIaaS). Furthermore, the resource bus allows for optimal resource allocation by connecting resource partitions within the CCF, while the resource management bus facilitates communication between the CCF and the MOF, allowing for dynamic allocation and management of resources.

III. AI/ML CROSS-LAYER PLATFORM (AI-CLATFORM)

The AI-CLatform is proposed as a fundamental component of the general 6G architecture, specifically designed to offer advanced AI capabilities that improve network performance,

optimize resource allocation, and enable the delivery of innovative services. Notably, this work focuses on the support of AI-CLatform (as the AI/ML process creator) to O-RAN (as the AI/ML model destination); however, the proposed AI-CLatform functional design, and the sequential flow is general-purpose and can be slightly adjusted to offer intelligence in the Core Network, CCF and/or MOF functions. As shown in Fig. 1, this framework includes several functional modules, each of which plays a significant role towards covering the successful implementation of each AI/ML stage, as detailed below.

A. Internal Blocks of AI-CLatform

To ensure the complete lifecycle of the AI/ML pipelines, including design, deployment, monitoring, updating, and retraining [20], AI-CLatform is composed of the following functional modules, each one implementing a particular AI/ML process within the comprehensive pipeline:

- 1) The Management Interface module: The basic point of interaction between AI-CLatform and other parts of the network. It manages the interactions among AIFs, ensuring smooth integration with other network systems.
- 2) AIF Performance Monitoring module: Continuously monitors, and assesses AIF training performance, detects anomalies within one AI/ML deployment, and indicates the potential impacts on other deployments in a proactive manner, ensuring overall system resilience and reliability.
- 3) AIF Orchestrator module: Manages the deployment and coordination of the AI/ML pipeline, and AI/ML models across the network, ensuring efficient resource allocation and AIF execution as needed.
- 4) AI/ML Function Database module: A repository of algorithms, modules, and tools that can be utilized across different NFs to support the deployment of AI/ML models across the network.
- 5) AI/ML Learning (retraining) module: Handles ongoing AI/ML model learning and retraining based on performance feedback, and data deviation detection from the AIF Performance Monitoring module, ensuring that the AI/ML models remain effective over time.
- 6) AI/ML Models Database module: Serves as a repository for AI models, enabling their retrieval and deployment across the network based on security and authorization mechanisms.
- 7) Network Digital Twin (NDT) module: Creates a virtual representation of the network to simulate and predict network behavior in a controlled environment prior to the entire deployment.
- 8) CI/CD interface: It stands for continuous integration/continuous development interface. It allows the rapid iteration of AI/ML models, constant maintenance, and testing in response to new insights.

Further details regarding the contribution of most of these modules to O-RAN for radio management will be specified in the following subsection.

B. AI/ML Lifecycles in O-RAN for Radio Management

This section outlines the proposed functional steps required to successfully realize AI/ML pipelines in radio resource optimization. The AI/ML lifecycle for radio management is divided into several phases, where each phase entails specific components of the AI-CLatform. Fig. 2 (initialization and training) and 3 (inference and monitoring) depict the complete sequence diagram (in UML representation), which disaggregates the AI/ML lifecycle across O-RAN and AI-CLatform in a general-purpose manner. For the ease of exposure, we indicatively focus on a critical radio resource task, namely the beamforming optimization. This optimization case illustrates (i) the AI-CLatform engagement in AI/ML model creation and (ii) how the AI/ML model can be applied to process multi-source signal measurements to intelligently determine optimal beam patterns for multi-element antennas, to minimize interference. The key phases of the proposed sequence can be defined as follows:

Fig. 2. AI/ML Model Initialization and Training in O-RAN

Fig. 3. AI/ML Model Inference, Monitoring, and Adaptive Retraining in O-RAN

- 1) Initial Setup and Training Phase: The process starts when the RAN Operator checks for a pre-trained ML

model to enable transfer learning. If such a model is available, it is retrieved and deployed to the Near-RT RIC. However, if this pre-trained model does not exist, the process of creating a new ML model training starts. During the training process, the AI/ML Training module cooperates with NDT to acquire or generate an adequate dataset, where NDT can be used either to complement missing datasets or as a training environment, based on the learning approach.

- 2) Model Deployment Phase: Following the training process or selection of a pre-trained model, the AI/ML Orchestrator deploys the model to the Near-RT RIC.
- 3) Continuous Operation and Performance Monitoring phase: During the inference, the performance of the model is continuously evaluated. For instance, the intelligent beamforming model employs ML inference to optimize beamforming patterns and ignore interfering signals in real-time. As soon as (i) any degradation in performance or (ii) KPI violation is detected, a retraining sequence is initiated.
- 4) Feedback and Adjustments Phase: The entire process is continuously assessed to ensure the efficiency of the model. Furthermore, feedback is provided to the RAN Operator to verify that the model is aligned with current demands.

IV. NUMERICAL SCENARIO: UTILIZING RNN FOR BEAMFORMING OPTIMIZATION

After describing the AI/ML lifecycle within the O-RAN environment, we present a proof-of-concept (PoC) implementation that focuses on beamforming optimization. This PoC demonstrates the practical capabilities of ML-driven approaches within the broader O-RAN framework. Specifically, we utilize an RNN model to predict the optimal complex feeding weights produced by one of the beamforming algorithms, showcasing (i) a key application of ML in O-RAN optimization and (ii) how the proposed AI/ML stages (through AI-CLatform) unfold. Numerical implementation covers the key AI/ML phases for training and evaluating the model, whereas descriptions are provided for the role of other modules to complement the entire AI/ML lifecycle.

A. Scenario Description & Simulation Setup

To investigate the beamforming problem in a controlled environment, the simulation setup starts with generating a dataset that functions as a basis for the training and evaluation of ML models. We consider null steering beamforming (NSB) [21], one of the most effective beamforming techniques to generate the optimum weights for different signal scenarios. NSB manages interference by adjusting the weighting coefficients of the antenna array elements while preserving the integrity of the signal of interest [21]. Since the NSB solution is time-consuming for a given input instance due to the iterations required, it cannot be used for fast real-time inference. Thus, given that AI/ML models can be effortlessly inferred in real-time with almost zero latency, we aim to train an AI/ML model that learns the NSB solution patterns. The training dataset is composed of

multiple solution instances of the traditional NSB approach, which determines the weight vector using the overall steering matrix \bar{A} . This matrix contains the steering vectors associated with the angles of arrival (AoA) of all received signals, involving both the wanted signal and the interfering signals. In this study, we consider a single base station equipped with a linear array containing 16 antenna elements. This array allows the base station to create a directed beam pattern toward the direction of the wanted signal while creating several nulls in the directions of the interfering signals to surpass their effects. Accordingly, the weight vector plays an essential role in defining the combination way of the signals from each element, producing the beam pattern of interest, which can be calculated using NSB as follows:

$$\mathbf{w} = \bar{A}(\bar{A}^H \bar{A})^{-1} \mathbf{e}_1 \quad (1)$$

where

- \mathbf{w} is the weight vector.
- \bar{A}^H is the Hermitian transpose of \bar{A} .
- \mathbf{e}_1 is a unit vector with the first element as 1 and the rest as 0

The steering matrix \bar{A} is given by:

$$\bar{A} = [\mathbf{a}(\theta_1), \mathbf{a}(\theta_2), \dots, \mathbf{a}(\theta_N)] \quad (2)$$

Each steering vector $\mathbf{a}(\theta_i)$ corresponds to a signal arriving at angle θ_i .

The training dataset includes pairs of AoAs and their corresponding optimal complex feeding weights (i.e. real and imaginary parts), with a total of 1 million records, partitioned in the following manner:

- 20% or 200,000 records, was allocated exclusively for final testing of the model.
- 80% or 800,000 records were allocated for training and validation purposes. Out of this 80%, we allocated 80% (640,000 records) for training and 20% (160,000 records) for validation.

In these simulations, we examine scenarios with several incoming signals, where the AoAs range from 30 to 150 degrees:

- 6 received signals (1 wanted + 5 interfering)
- 7 received signals (1 wanted + 6 interfering)
- 8 received signals (1 wanted + 7 interfering)

In the following subsection, we present the configuration of the proposed RNN model, designed to simulate the performance of the NSB algorithm in real-time applications.

B. Neural Network Characteristics

The primary objective of this section is to evaluate the effectiveness of an RNN-based beamformer in efficiently learning to predict the optimal complex feeding weights produced by NSB based on the AoAs information. As a result, RNN-produced weights can effectively manage interfering signals when applied to an antenna array, providing accurate suggestive actions to be applied on the RU of O-RAN. RNNs are a particular kind of NN that excels at processing structured input data. Even though conventionally utilized

for sequential data with temporal dependencies [22], in this beamforming application, we leverage RNNs for their ability to efficiently model complex spatial relationships among multiple input features (AoAs) simultaneously.

The input layer in RNN is designed to accept the number of features corresponding to the number of incoming signals (6,7, or 8). The input layer is followed by two simple RNN layers with 128, and 64 units, respectively. Following the RNN layers, the network includes two dense layers with 128 and 64 units respectively, both employing the rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation function. The architecture concludes with an output layer of 32 units utilizing the hyperbolic tangent activation function (tanh), designed to represent the complex feeding weights for the 16 array elements. As a proactive step to avoid overfitting and improve the training process, we apply ReduceLRonPlateau, which adapts the learning rate during the training process by reducing it by a factor of 0.2 when the validation loss plateaus for 5 consecutive epochs. Furthermore, we employ the EarlyStopping technique with a patience of 10 epochs for further monitoring of the validation loss. Table I lists the ML model learning parameters.

TABLE I
RNN CONFIGURATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Initial Learning Rate	0.001
Loss Function	Mean Squared Error (MSE)
Batch Size	64
Maximum Epochs	100

Fig. 4. Loss comparison (Fixed learning rate vs Adaptive learning rate)

C. Model Performance Assessment

To thoroughly assess the performance of the proposed RNN model, we employ several evaluation metrics beyond the primary loss function MSE. These include the mean absolute error (MAE), which calculates the average size of the prediction errors without taking their direction into account. Additionally, we incorporate the coefficient of determination, or R^2 score, which provides a measure of how well the model explains the variability of the target variable.

Before delving through the simulation results, and to prove the efficiency of the adaptive learning rate approach, a comparative study using the simplest scenario of 6 incoming signals is performed. Two identical RNN models are trained: one with a fixed learning rate of 0.001 and another with our proposed adaptive learning rate strategy. The loss comparison plot depicted in Fig. 4 indicates that both models start with similar behavior, nevertheless, the scenario with an adaptive learning rate approach shows faster initial convergence, more stable behavior, better generalization, and lower final loss values.

Accordingly, Figs 5,6 illustrate the training and validation results of the RNN model that is configured to process several numbers of received signals. After the completion of the training for the 100 iterations, we evaluate the model performance using the predefined test set, as presented in Table II.

TABLE II
RNN MODEL PERFORMANCE EVALUATION WITH VARYING SIGNAL COUNTS

Signals	MSE	MAE	R ² Score
6	0.01165	0.08643	0.96385
7	0.01825	0.10770	0.94183
8	0.02115	0.11560	0.93059

Fig. 5. Training and validation Loss across different signal configurations

The evaluation results of the RNN model indicate its strong predictive capability and robust performance across varying levels of signal complexity. The model exhibits high accuracy, with high R^2 scores and low MSE, and MAE values, indicating strong predictive powers. It is worth noting that, as the number of signals increases from 6 to 8, we observe a gradual and expected degradation in performance. The R^2 score decreases indicating a slight 3.4% reduction in explanatory power. Concurrently, the MSE, and MAE increase. Regardless of this trend, the model maintains strong predictive performance even in the most complex scenarios. This resilience, coupled with the ability of the model to handle increasing numbers of signals with only minor performance decline, suggests it could be a scalable and efficient

Fig. 6. Training and validation MAE across different signal configurations

alternative to traditional beamforming methods in real-world applications.

D. Scenario implementation using AI-CLatform

This section summarizes the engagement of AI-CLatform in implementing the presented scenario in real network setups. Without loss of generality, we assume that the dataset used for the beamforming optimization (see section IV-A) has been already collected and stored in the database of the AI/ML Training Module. This can be done by using the radio resource collection principles defined in O-RAN [7], which is achieved either (i) by sending AoA measurements from RU to DU via an open fronthaul link, and then forwarding the so-called E2 reports from DU towards the Near-RT RIC through E2 open interface (via publish-subscribe mechanics over SCTP protocol) or (ii) by collecting the training data through the O1 interface, which is used to convey radio resource data from the DU/CU towards the M&O layer. Although the general workflow shown in Fig. 3 can be easily adopted, below we ignore the engagement of the NDT for the ease of exposure and for simplicity. Thus, to concretely present the proposed framework, the AI-CLatform-based workflow required for training, evaluating, and finally deploying the beamforming optimizer could be outlined as follows:

Step 1: Initially, the RAN operator (or another RAN entity) sends an ML model training request towards the AI/ML Orchestrator in the form of a description file that specifies the targeted optimization scenario and the required dataset. **Step 2:** The AI/ML Orchestrator initiates the model training by notifying the AI/ML Training module. Upon using the required model functions (see section IV-B), parameters (see Table IV-B) and ML libraries (for RNN algorithm) provided by the AI/ML Functions Database, AI/ML Training module performs the training of the beamforming model, as presented in section IV-A & IV-B. **Step 3:** The trained beamforming optimizer is stored in a memory-efficient format (e.g. as pickle or docker image) in the AI/ML Models Database for possible future retrieval. **Step 4:** AI/ML Orchestrator activates the model deployment from the AI/ML Models Database towards the Near-RT RIC (as an xApp package).

An E2 setup procedure is also performed to initiate a control loop between Near-RT RIC and the E2 node (i.e. the DU managing the antenna patterns of the respective RU). **Step 5:** Inference data (i.e. AoA measurements) associated with the managed RU are received periodically, asynchronously, or upon request (depending on the xApp configuration parameters defined at the deployment phase). AoA measures are fed in the RNN to obtain the AI-assisted beamforming steering matrix. The input and output (model suggestions) data are exchanged during the inference rounds to and from the xApp flow over the E2 interface. **Step 6:** Periodically or on alert, evaluation data are sent in the Performance Monitoring module. Performance can be KPI-defined by measuring the wanted signal isolation, the achieved data rate, or the interference levels upon applying the beamforming patterns suggested by the ML model. **Step 7:** If performance degradation or KPI violation is observed, Performance Monitoring module invokes the AI/ML Orchestrator to reactivate a retraining process with an updated dataset and/or model configuration. Steps 3-7 are repeated over time to provide continuous intelligence loops for beamforming optimization.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a comprehensive framework for AI/ML lifecycles within the O-RAN architecture, specifically customized for radio resource management in emerging 6G networks is discussed. We introduced the AI-CLatform, a general-purpose framework, with a detailed presentation of complete AI lifecycles and their interactions with O-RAN. Finally in this paper, a practical use case demonstrating the application of the AI-CLatform framework, focusing on intelligent beamforming is introduced. The RNN-based approach showed robust performance across varying numbers of signals, preserving high accuracy in prediction even as scenario complexity increased, highlighting the potential of the RNN model for enhancing beamforming techniques in complex 6G network environments.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. Sullivan, A. Brighente, S. A. P. Kumar, and M. Conti, "5G security challenges and solutions: A review by OSI layers," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 116294–116314, 2021.
- [2] P. Gkonis, A. Giannopoulos, P. Trakadas, X. Masip-Bruin, and F. D'Andria, "A survey on iot-edge-cloud continuum systems: status, challenges, use cases, and open issues," *Future Internet*, vol. 15, no. 12, p. 383, 2023.
- [3] S. Spantideas, A. Giannopoulos, M. A. Cambeiro, O. Trullols-Cruces, E. Atxutegi, and P. Trakadas, "Intelligent mission critical services over beyond 5g networks: Control loop and proactive overload detection," in *2023 International Conference on Smart Applications, Communications and Networking (SmartNets)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [4] W. Jiang, B. Han, M. A. Habibi, and H. D. Schotten, "The road towards 6g: A comprehensive survey," *IEEE Open J. Commun. Soc.*, vol. 2, pp. 334–366, 2021.
- [5] D. Mur, A. Gavras, M. Ghoraiishi, H. Hrasnica, and A. Kaloxylou, "Ai and ml-enablers for beyond 5g networks," *White Paper G*, vol. 5, 2021.
- [6] T. Chen, S. Kuklinski, E. Pateromichelakis, K. Samdanis, A. Kourtis, N. Nikaein, and A. Skarmeta, "Service-oriented architecture evolution towards 6G networks," in *2023 IEEE Conference on Standards for Communications and Networking (CSCN)*. IEEE, Nov. 2023.
- [7] A. Giannopoulos, S. Spantideas, N. Kapsalis, P. Gkonis, L. Sarakis, C. Capsalis, M. Vecchio, and P. Trakadas, "Supporting intelligence in disaggregated open radio access networks: Architectural principles, ai/ml workflow, and use cases," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 39580–39595, 2022.
- [8] T. Karamplias, S. T. Spantideas, A. E. Giannopoulos, P. Gkonis, N. Kapsalis, and P. Trakadas, "Towards closed-loop automation in 5g open ran: Coupling an open-source simulator with xapps," in *2022 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 232–237.
- [9] R. Britto, T. Murphy, M. Iovene, L. Jonsson, M. Erol-Kantarci, and B. Kovács, "Telecom AI native systems in the age of generative AI – an engineering perspective," 2023.
- [10] W. Wu, C. Zhou, M. Li, H. Wu, H. Zhou, N. Zhang, X. S. Shen, and W. Zhuang, "AI-native network slicing for 6G networks," *IEEE Wirel. Commun.*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 96–103, Feb. 2022.
- [11] A. Alhammedi, I. Shaya, A. A. El-Saleh, M. H. Azmi, Z. H. Ismail, L. Kouhalvandi, and S. A. Saad, "Artificial intelligence in 6G wireless networks: Opportunities, applications, and challenges," *Int. J. Intell. Syst.*, vol. 2024, pp. 1–27, Mar. 2024.
- [12] M. Costola, O. Hinz, M. Nofer, and L. Pelizzon, "Machine learning sentiment analysis, COVID-19 news and stock market reactions," *Res. Int. Bus. Fin.*, vol. 64, no. 101881, p. 101881, Jan. 2023.
- [13] K. Samdanis, A. N. Abbou, J. Song, and T. Taleb, "AI/ML service enablers and model maintenance for beyond 5G networks," *IEEE Netw.*, vol. 37, no. 5, pp. 162–172, Sep. 2023.
- [14] T. Chen, X. Zhang, M. You, G. Zheng, and S. Lambotaran, "A GNN-based supervised learning framework for resource allocation in wireless IoT networks," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 1712–1724, Feb. 2022.
- [15] A. A. Puspitasari, T. T. An, M. H. Alsharif, and B. M. Lee, "Emerging technologies for 6G communication networks: Machine learning approaches," *Sensors (Basel)*, vol. 23, no. 18, Sep. 2023.
- [16] M. A. Uusitalo, M. Ericson, B. Richerzhagen, E. U. Soykan, P. Ruge-land, G. Fettweis, D. Sabella, G. Wikstrom, M. Boldi, M.-H. Hamon, H. D. Schotten, V. Ziegler, E. C. Strinati, M. Latva-aho, P. Serrano, Y. Zou, G. Carrozzo, J. Martrat, G. Stea, P. Demestichas, A. Parssinen, and T. Svensson, "Hexa-X the european 6G flagship project," in *2021 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*. IEEE, Jun. 2021.
- [17] J. Fonseca, M. Khadmaoui-Bichouna, B. Mendes, P. Duarte, M. Araújo, D. Corujo, I. Sanchez-Navarro, E. A. Matencio-Escolar, P. Salva-Garcia, J. M. Alcaraz-Calero, and Q. Wang, "6G BRAINS topology-aware industry-grade network slice management and orchestration," in *2023 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*. IEEE, Jun. 2023.
- [18] E. C. Strinati, G. C. Alexandropoulos, V. Sciancalepore, M. Di Renzo, H. Wymeersch, D.-T. Phan-Huy, M. Crozzoli, R. D'Errico, E. De Carvalho, P. Popovski, P. Di Lorenzo, L. Bastianelli, M. Belouar, J. E. Mascolo, G. Gradoni, S. Phang, G. Lerosey, and B. Denis, "Wireless environment as a service enabled by reconfigurable intelligent surfaces: The RISE-6G perspective," in *2021 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*. IEEE, Jun. 2021.
- [19] P. Szmaja, A. Fornés-Leal, I. Lacalle, C. E. Palau, M. Ganzha, W. Pawłowski, M. Paprzycki, and J. Schabbink, "ASSIST-IoT: A modular implementation of a reference architecture for the next generation internet of things," *Electronics (Basel)*, vol. 12, no. 4, p. 854, Feb. 2023.
- [20] V. P. Kafle, T. Hirayama, T. Miyazawa, M. Jibiki, and H. Harai, "Network control and management automation: Architecture standardization perspective," *IEEE Commun. Stand. Mag.*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 106–114, Sep. 2021.
- [21] M. R. R. Khan and V. Tuzlukov, "Null steering beamforming for wireless communication system using genetic algorithm," in *2011 IEEE International Conference on Microwave Technology & Computational Electromagnetics*. IEEE, May 2011.
- [22] A. Sherstinsky, "Fundamentals of recurrent neural network (RNN) and long short-term memory (LSTM) network," *Physica D*, vol. 404, no. 132306, p. 132306, Mar. 2020.